

Supplementary Material S2.- List of the islands considered in the study.

Azores (comprising the islands of Flores, Corvo, Graciosa, Terceira, São Jorge, Pico, Faial, São Miguel and Santa Maria), Madeira (Madeira and Porto Santo), Cabo Verde (Santo Antão, São Vicente, São Nicolau, Sal, Boavista, Maio, Santiago, Fogo, Brava), Canary islands (El Hierro, La Palma, La Gomera, Tenerife, Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura, Lanzarote), Balearic islands (Mallorca, Menorca, Ibiza and Formentera), Sicily and circumsicilian islands (Favignana, Levanzo, Marettimo, Ustica, Alicudi, Filicudi, Lipari, Panarea, Salina, Stromboli, Vulcano, Lampedusa, Linosa, Pantelleria), Malta, Sardinia and circumsardinian islands (Asinara, Piana di Asinara, Porri, Maddalena, Caprera, Tavolara, Spargi, Molara, Santo Stefano, Santa Maria, Budelli, Razzoli, Li Nibali, Mortorio, Barrettini, Sant'Antioco, San Pietro, Vacca, Toro), Corsica, Tuscan Archipelago (Gorgona, Capraia, Elba, Pianosa, Montecristo, Giglio), Pontine islands (Ponza, Zannone, Ventotene, Santo Stefano, Vivara, Procida, Capri), Tremiti islands (San Nicola, San Domino, Capraia), Croatian islands (Sveta Katarina, Brijuni, Krk, Plavnik, Cres, Lošinj, Srakane Male, Ilovik, Unije, Veli Osir, Vele Orjule, Sveti Petar, Rab, Pag, Silba, Dugi Otok, Ugljan, Rava, Iž, Pašman, Kornat, Murter, Zlarin, Čiovo, Šolta, Brač, Hvar, Vis, Biševo, Sveti Andrija, Sušac, Korčula, Mljet, Lopud, Šipán, Žut, Lavsa), Greek islands (Crete, Rhodes, Kefalonia, Corfù, Lefkada, Zakynthos, Naxos, Euboea, Kythira, Tinos, Milos, Aegina, Syros, Thasos, Paros, Skopelos, Karpathos, Chios, Kos, Kea, Santorini, Salamis, Skyros, Nisyros, Lesbos) and Cyprus.